

Neutron reflectivity study of grafted poly(ethylene glycol) in the presence of an aqueous bovine serum albumin solution^ψ

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We have used specular neutron reflection, employing contrast variation by isotopic substitution, to probe the structure of a poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) coated silicon surface. A PEG molecule with a molar mass of $M_w = 5000 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$ and a trimethoxysilane end group was chemisorbed onto the silica surface. The grafted layer was found to possess an average thickness of $\sim 85 \text{ \AA}$ in its solvated state and the surface coverage was $\Gamma_{\text{PEG}} = 1.1 \pm 0.2 \text{ mg m}^{-2}$, corresponding to an area per molecule of $A_{\text{PEG}} = 770 \pm 230 \text{ \AA}^2$. For this surface coverage, brush formation is indicated since the layer thickness is found to be approximately three times the radius of gyration, R_g , of the PEG molecule, and the average area per molecule is consistent with overlapping polymer chains. We have further investigated the structure of the PEG layer when bovine serum albumin (BSA) is present in the aqueous solution. The protein adsorption measurements were conducted at $\text{pH} = 5$, close to the isoelectric point of BSA, where its maximum adsorption is found when adsorbed on to silica, and the concentration of the protein solution was 0.1 g dm^{-3} . When BSA is present in solution the thickness of the PEG layer is reduced to $\sim 55 \text{ \AA}$, but, within the sensitivity of the present measurements, there is no evidence for the formation of an adsorbed BSA layer. Control experiments were performed against a hydrophilic silica surface.

Poly(ethylene oxide), PEO, remains almost unique as an example of a neutral, hydrophilic polymer. Because of this status, PEO is employed in many applications involving amphiphilic block copolymers composed of PEO blocks and a relatively more hydrophobic block, for instance poly(propylene oxide) in the Pluronic series of copolymers¹. In their applications these polymers act as emulsion-stabilisers, wetting agents and so forth. The use of PEO – especially in its shorter-chain poly(ethylene glycol), PEG, polymers – as a surface coating used in the formation of protein resistant surfaces has also attracted, in addition to experimental studies, significant theoretical attention². Despite some issues regarding its long-term stability and complex forming ability with some ions³, PEG meets many of the necessary criteria to be suitable

for acting as a protein resistant surface^{4,5}. Neutral, hydrophilic polymers, such as PEG, tend to have minimal or very weak electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions with protein molecules in aqueous solutions, their dynamic polymer chain acts to disrupt hydrogen bonding of water to the polymer chain, and a low dielectric constant reduces the long range van der Waals attraction acting across a film of the polymer². However, in addition to these favourable interactions, the mechanism for the resistance of PEG to protein adsorption is believed to be a steric-stabilisation effect⁶. Upon approach of the adsorbing protein molecule to the PEG surface a repulsive force develops because the available volume per polymer segment and hence the conformational freedom is reduced. This elastic component of the stabilisation effect is ac-

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

accompanied by an osmotic contribution. Owing to the repulsion between PEG and protein, the PEG concentration at the surface becomes enhanced as the protein approaches the surface and a further repulsive interaction develops because the conformational entropy is further reduced. The result of the osmotic repulsion is that the PEG may become compressed or may become further self-entangled. Which one of these outcomes occurs depends on the grafting density of the polymer film.

In this article we report the results of preliminary experiments in which we have concentrated on examining three aspects of a PEG-grafted surface and its relation to protein resistance. First, we have determined the conformation of the chemisorbed PEG molecules using neutron reflection and employing contrast variation by isotopic substitution. Although chemisorbed PEG films have been examined by various means (including XPS, X-ray and neutron reflection⁷⁻¹⁹, ellipsometry, AFM etc.²⁰⁻²⁴), experiments seeking the level of information attainable using contrast variation remain unreported. Second, we compare the structure of chemisorbed films obtained by preparing the surface with a one-shot grafting methodology²⁰ with adsorbed amounts determined for PEG layers prepared using post-grafting methodologies. Such post-grafted surface layers have been reported to provide a satisfactory degree of protein resistance^{7,25}. Our PEG surface was produced by grafting trimethoxysilane end-terminated poly(ethylene glycol) with a molar mass of 5000 g mol⁻¹ on to the silica surface of a silicon substrate. Finally, we have examined, as far as possible using neutron reflectometry, the protein resistance of the PEG surface with particular attention paid to examining the response of the chemisorbed PEG film to the presence of protein in the solution rather than detecting small adsorbed amounts of protein. In the protein adsorption experiments we have chosen bovine serum albumin as our model protein (BSA) since it is a much-studied protein whose structure, dimensions, and amino acid sequence are well documented²⁶. We have compared the adsorption of BSA (concentration, $c = 0.1 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$) from its aqueous buffered solution at pH = 5 on a PEG-coated surface with that on a bare hydrophilic (control) surface. The pH chosen is close to the isoelectric point of BSA where its adsorption on to a surface is expected to maximise owing to minimisation of the electrostatic repulsion between like molecules.

Experimental

Materials :

D₂O (99.9 atom % D) was obtained from Fluorochem,

and de-ionised H₂O was purified using an Elgar Maxima UHQ water purification system. The end-functionalised poly(ethylene glycol) molecule used was [*O*-(2-(trimethoxysilyl)ethyl)-*O'*-methyl-polyethylene glycol-5000] with molar mass 5000 g mol⁻¹,

synthesised by Shearwater Polymers and purchased from Fluka. The bovine serum albumin (BSA) (>97%) was obtained from Sigma and was essentially fatty acid free (<0.005%). Phosphate-citrate (0.2 mol dm⁻³ dibasic sodium phosphate and 0.1 mol dm⁻³ citric acid) buffer tablets at pH = 5 were purchased from Sigma. The buffered solutions were prepared with D₂O as well as with the different isotopic water mixtures and filtered several times to remove any undissolved particles.

Grafting of PEG layer :

The method of PEG grafting used is related to the one-shot method described by Yang and Yu²⁰. Before the polymer grafting, however, the silicon surfaces were cleaned using a hot solution of hydrogen peroxide and ammonia in water 1/1/5 (v/v) rendering the surfaces entirely hydrophilic²⁷. One of the silicon blocks cleaned in this manner was then stored in UHQ water until use, whereas the other block was further treated with the PEG coupling agent.

Before grafting the PEG chains on to the silica surface, the silicon blocks were sequentially cleaned with methanol/chloroform mixtures with proportions 3/1, 1/3, and 0/1 (v/v) in an ultrasonic bath to chemically remove all the water from their surfaces. The PEG grafting proceeded by the base-promoted coupling of the trimethoxysilane group of the PEG molecule with surface silanol groups. The PEG self-assembled monolayers were obtained by refluxing the silicon blocks for 24 h in a toluene solution containing 5 wt% triethylamine and 0.5 wt% end-functionalised PEG under a dry nitrogen atmosphere. After grafting, the samples were ultrasonically cleaned to remove from the surface any physically adsorbed polymer chains, which may further react with water.

Protein adsorption :

The non-denatured solvated protein molecule has an ellipsoidal shape with major and minor axes approximately equal to 140 and 40 Å, respectively. The overall stoichiometric composition, C₃₀₇₁H₄₈₁₉N₈₁₆O₉₂₆S₄₀, giving a molar mass of approximately 69000 g mol⁻¹, was determined from the amino acid sequence²⁶. The number of protons and, hence, the stoichiometric composition is,

however, variable with pH. For the chosen sequence, the number of exchangeable hydrogens in the molecule of BSA was calculated to be 1112. The iso-electric point of BSA is at pH = 4.8²⁸. Scattering length densities of BSA in different water contrasts were calculated (see Table 1) according to the method employed by Su *et al.*¹², assuming that all labile hydrogens are exchanged in the same ratio as the content of D₂O in the H₂O/D₂O mixtures, which is a reasonable approximation for globular proteins²⁹. The adsorption of the BSA was performed on the bare silicon and the PEG-coated substrates. Protein was added to phosphate-citrate buffered solutions at pH = 5 to produce protein solutions with concentration 0.1 g dm⁻³. Protein adsorption was conducted *in situ* inside the sample cells used for the reflectivity measurements. Protein adsorption was allowed to proceed for *ca.* four hours before commencing the measurements. This is believed to be sufficient length of time to achieve a steady adsorption state.

angle of incidence of the neutron beam and λ is the neutron wavelength. The reflectivity measurements were conducted on the reflectometer SURF at the ISIS Facility, Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Didcot, UK³¹. SURF is a time-of-flight reflectometer and the neutrons have wavelengths in the range $0.5 < \lambda/\text{\AA} < 6.5$. Reflectivities over a wide range of momentum transfer were measured by using several grazing incidence angles. The neutrons, incident through a single-crystal silicon block, were reflected from the silicon/water interface and detected by a ³He single-detector. In these measurements the resolution was $\delta\theta/\theta \approx 3\%$. The sample cell used has been reported elsewhere³².

Data analysis :

The measured $R(Q)$ data are then analysed in terms of a structural model. In this work we have fitted the data using simple layer models, and calculated the reflectivity using the optical matrix method. In addition to layer thicknesses and compositions, the area per molecule and

Table 1. Scattering lengths^a and scattering length densities^b of the materials used in this study

Molecule	Scattering length $b_j/\text{\AA}$	Material	Scattering length density $Nb/10^{-6} \text{\AA}^{-2}$
SiOx	1.574×10^{-4}	D ₂ O	6.35
PEG	0.0046	H ₂ O	-0.56
BSA in D ₂ O	0.2711	Si (substrate)	2.07
BSA in CMSiOx	0.2276	CMSi water	2.20
BSA in CMSi	0.2020	SiOx (silica)	3.60
		CMSiOx water	3.75
		BSA ^c (in D ₂ O, CMSiOx, CMSi)	3.42, 2.87, 2.55
		PEG ^d	0.56

^aScattering lengths taken from Ref.⁴³.

^bDensities at 25°C used for calculating scattering length densities taken from CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics⁴⁴.

^cScattering length densities of BSA calculated following Su *et al.*¹².

^dPEG scattering length density from Jones and Richards⁴⁵.

Neutron reflectometry :

Neutron reflectometry is a scattering technique used to determine the neutron refractive index profile normal to the interface. Full details of the technique are given elsewhere^{30,31}. The refractive index is related to the material composition and hence a composition profile can be determined. In an experiment, the reflectivity, $R(Q)$, is measured as a function of momentum transfer, $Q=4\pi \sin \theta/\lambda$, normal to the interface, where θ is the grazing

adsorbed amount can be determined. To reduce the ambiguity of the model fitting we have employed contrast variation of the aqueous solvent, and have used aqueous solutions with refractive indices matched to those of silicon, silicon oxide and deuterium oxide. Ideally, one would fit the $R(Q)$ profiles for different contrasts simultaneously. We have analysed the data using two approaches. In the first approach we have proposed a layer model and assumed the number density of the PEG. The analysis pro-

ceeds by proposing a composition for the layer in the multilayer model being examined, and allowing the layer thickness and roughness to float while the scattering length densities (for the three contrasts) remain fixed at the calculated values based on the presumed composition. This process is repeated for a number of compositions until satisfactory fits are obtained. For solvated polymers, however, the number density is not necessarily known. Therefore we have adopted a second method. In this method the thickness, roughness and scattering length densities are floated and the resulting scattering length densities are analysed in the following manner. Consider a layer of a structural model with, for a given contrast, a scattering length density $(Nb)_i$ determined by non-linear least-squares fitting. The number density of polymer in a layer can be written as

$$N_p = \frac{(Nb)_i - (Nb)_w}{\phi_p b_p} + \frac{(Nb)_w}{b_p} \quad (1)$$

where N_p is the number density of species p when $\phi_p = 1$, $(Nb)_i$ is the scattering length density of the layer, b_p and ϕ_p are the scattering length per molecule and the volume fraction composition, respectively, of species p , and $(Nb)_w$ is the scattering length density of the water. There are two unknown parameters (ϕ_p and N_p) in this relationship. For three water contrasts there are three such relationships like eq. (1) with only two unknown parameters. If we perform the analyses, as we have done, by fitting the reflectivity profiles from the three water contrasts simultaneously and constraining the layer thickness to be the same for the corresponding layer in the model for each contrast, we determine a set of $(Nb)_i$. Substituting the $(Nb)_i$ into expressions of the form of eq. (1) and then plotting graphs of N_p versus ϕ_p on the same set of axes allows us to find the coordinate (N_p, ϕ_p) where the three graphs intersect. These intersection plots can be used to determine the layer composition and any uncertainty in that composition. If the three lines do intersect, the model is satisfactory; if not, recourse to a more complex model is required, i.e. the intersection method is self-consistent.

Results and discussion

Characterisation of the 'control' hydrophilic silica surface :

Fits to the reflectivity data correspond to an oxide layer with a thickness of $11 \pm 3 \text{ \AA}$, roughness of $\sim 5 \text{ \AA}$, and containing $10 \pm 1\%$ water. This layer thickness is consistent with measurements made on other silicon blocks

from the same batch cleaned by the same procedure. The water in the oxide layer is most likely present in the roughened exterior of the layer as opposed to the layer itself being porous.

Characterisation of the PEG-treated silica surface :

Measured and fitted reflectivity profiles from the PEG-coated silica/water surface are shown in Fig. 1 for the three contrasts of water. Reasonable representation of the experimental data is obtained with a two-layer model, composed of a layer containing $12.5 \pm 3.0\%$ PEG with a thickness of $85 \pm 10 \text{ \AA}$ capping a $9.5 \pm 3.0 \text{ \AA}$ oxide layer. The roughness between the PEG layer and bulk water – or rather diffuseness of the PEG-solution interface – is of the order of 40 \AA . If it is assumed that all the end-grafted PEG is confined in this region, i.e. if there are no extended dilute polymer tails, the average area per PEG molecule extracted from the model fitting is $A_{\text{PEG}} = 900 \pm 230 \text{ \AA}^2$, which converts to an adsorbed amount, $\Gamma_{\text{PEG}} = 0.9 \pm 0.2 \text{ mg m}^{-2}$. The radius of gyration for the PEG molecule with molar mass $M_w = 5000 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$ is calculated to be 24 \AA under these solvent conditions³³. The thickness of the PEG film is in the region of $2\text{--}3 \times R_g$, which suggests it to be in the weak brush regime. The distance between adjacent centres of the PEG molecules, $r = (A_{\text{PEG}})^{1/2} \approx 30 \text{ \AA} \sim R_g$, indicates that the grafting density lies at the boundary of mushroom and brush-like behaviour.

The structure of the PEG layer is, for the given molar mass of PEG, consistent with the film thicknesses and surface coverages found by other workers using other techniques. Klein and Luckham³⁴ have measured, using a surface force apparatus, the force-distance curves of two approaching non-grafted PEG (with molar masses of 4×10^4 and $1.6 \times 10^5 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) films on mica in $0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KNO}_3$ at $\text{pH} = 6$, which is a good aqueous solvent for these polymers. They find that repulsion sets in at $(6 \pm 1) \times R_g$, i.e. for films of thickness $\sim 3 \times R_g$. This value ($\equiv 3 \times 24 \text{ \AA} = 72 \text{ \AA}$) corresponds approximately to the film thickness, 85 \AA we find for the much lower molar mass polymer studied here. The surface coverage of PEG found by us can be compared with values determined by Sofia *et al.*²⁵ for linear PEG molecules with similar molar mass. From their data a surface coverage of $\Gamma_{\text{PEG}} \approx 1.0 \text{ mg m}^{-2}$ is achieved using a grafting solution with concentration of 10 wt\% PEG for polymers with molar mass $M_w = 3400 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$ and 10000 g mol^{-1} . In our experiments with PEG of $M_w = 5000 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$, the grafting solution contained 0.5 wt\% PEG to obtain an adsorbed layer with a comparable density. It

should be noted that our grafting solution concentration, c is $\sim 0.25 c_{\text{crit}}$. In this respect, we wish to point out that the approach we have adopted in grafting the PEG layer involves a single stage, base-promoted coupling reaction. The related work we have discussed above, however, has PEG monolayers produced by a two-stage, post-grafting methodology. This alternative method involves coupling tresylated PEG onto an aminosilane-coupled monolayer. It appears that both grafting methodologies result in polymer layers with similar, reasonably low grafting densities. Irvine *et al.*⁷ have performed a similar study of linear and star PEG molecules, and have optimised the grafting density to minimise protein adsorption. They find that tuning the 'goodness' of the solvent by K_2SO_4 additions can help to optimise the grafting density for linear PEG.

Fig. 1. Measured (symbols) and modelled (solid lines) reflectivity data of the PEG-coated silicon/water interface prior to BSA adsorption for the three different water contrasts matched to D_2O (o), silicon oxide, CMSiOx (∇), and silicon, CMSi (\square).

Adsorption of BSA on hydrophilic silica :

After adsorption of BSA onto the hydrophilic silica surface, reflectivity profiles were measured for the three contrasts of water. The adsorbed BSA layer on the silica surface is found to have a thickness of $28 \pm 5 \text{ \AA}$, and it contains $50 \pm 5\%$ protein. The oxide layer was modelled by considering it to contain 90% silica, 5% water and 5% BSA. From these parameters, the average area per BSA molecule on the surface is, $A_{\text{BSA}} = 5660 \pm 600 \text{ \AA}^2$. This is consistent with a model with a side-on adsorption configuration in which the BSA molecule adsorbs with its long-axis parallel to the surface. The thickness 28 \AA

is, however, slightly less than the width, 40 \AA of the solvated molecule. This could possibly be due to some distortion of the molecule resulting from its adsorption or due to encroachment of the BSA into the oxide layer. The adsorbed amount is found to be $\Gamma_{\text{BSA}} = 2.05 \pm 0.20 \text{ mg m}^{-2}$.

The results we find agree with those reported by Lu and co-workers^{11,12} who have been examining the effect of protein adsorption on hydrophilic silica surfaces using neutron reflectometry. For conditions corresponding to those we have applied, they report a protein film with a thickness of 37 \AA . However, taking into account the protein residing in the roughness of the oxide layer, the protein film we have examined has an overall thickness $\sim 35 \text{ \AA}$ which is very close to the value reported by Lu and co-workers. Lu and co-workers reported an adsorbed amount Γ_{BSA} to be $1.8\text{--}2.4 \text{ mg m}^{-2}$ for solution concentrations in the range $0.005\text{--}0.500 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$. Slight differences in these values can be attributed to differences in the employed surface preparation techniques.

Structure of the PEG film in the presence of BSA solution :

Measured and modelled reflectivity data are shown in Fig. 2 for the PEG-modified surface in contact with a solution containing BSA. Analysis of the data reveal that the thickness of the PEG layer is reduced from $\sim 85 \text{ \AA}$ to $\sim 55 \text{ \AA}$, indicating that the presence of BSA in the solution causes the polymer film to become compressed. There is no evidence for a distinct layer of protein adsorbed to the PEG film. Models can be applied to the surface with a very thin and dilute ($\sim 3 \text{ \AA}$, $\phi_{\text{BSA}} < 0.05$) layer of BSA, but such models have little physical support since realistic material balance considerations are not satisfied. This compression of the polymer film is consistent with the conjectured mechanism of protein resistance by BSA mentioned in the introduction. For PEG grafting densities lying at the mushroom-brush borderline, the osmotic contribution to the repulsive interaction between PEG and protein results in film compression rather than further polymer entanglement.

It appears that the surface is reasonably resistant to secondary (discrete film) adsorption of bovine serum albumin. The current measurements do not possess the sensitivity to examine whether primary (interstitial) adsorption of protein to the un-treated regions of the silica surface lying between the chemisorbed PEG molecules has occurred. However, the grafting density and resulting A_{PEG} suggests there is insufficient surface area between PEG molecules for BSA to adsorb.

Fig. 2. Measured (symbols) and modelled (solid lines) reflectivity data of the PEG-coated silicon/solution interface after BSA adsorption for the three different water contrasts matched to D₂O (○), silicon oxide, CMSiOx (▽), and silicon, CMSi (□).

Adsorption of proteins on related surfaces :

The extent of protein adsorption on a surface is not solely determined by the pH and ionic strength of solution, which control the lateral electrostatic interaction between adjacent protein molecules. Further to these contributions, the nature and properties of the PEG layer also play a major role in determining the extent of protein adsorption. Sofia *et al.*²⁵ studied the adsorption of the three proteins, cytochrome-c, human serum albumin, and fibronectin on the linear and star forms of poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) mentioned above. They found that the degree of adsorption is a function of both the PEO grafting density and the size of the protein molecule. Irvine *et al.*⁷ similarly found that the surfaces grafted with the optimum density of polymer showed resistance to protein adsorption of cytochrome-c and human serum albumin, except for a small amount of adsorption observed on a many-armed star polymer-coated surface. In this case, it is believed that the protein molecules can adsorb in the vacancies between the grafted polymer molecules.

Self-assembled monolayers offer excellent model systems for investigating protein adsorption on surfaces with differing degrees of hydrophobicity and chemical functionality^{8,17-19,35,36}. Experiments have been reported using self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) of ethylene oxide oligomers³⁷ as the model systems, representing PEG^{8,38}. From these studies much can be inferred on how the different factors, such as surface chain density

and chain length, influence the adsorption process. However, it should be noted that such systems are significantly different from a polymeric system in which chain-end effects are less prominent and osmotic interactions become increasingly important.

The possible concerns about the PEG and its long-term biocompatibility were voiced earlier in the introduction. New polymers are being developed with more favourable properties. These include the new cross-linked hydrogel polymers incorporated with phosphorylcholine groups and dodecyl chains³⁹. Lu and co-workers⁴⁰ have recently been studying the protein resistance of such surfaces. Another type of polymer being developed for its biocompatibility has been investigated by Hester *et al.*⁴¹. They have studied self-healing surfaces of polymer membranes by surface segregation. The surface was composed of a comb graft copolymer consisting of a poly(methyl methacrylate) backbone and poly(ethylene oxide) grafts in a poly(vinylidene fluoride) matrix. Such a surface resists the adsorption of BSA. A further example of new protein-friendly materials is graft copolymers of poly(L-lysine)-g-PEO⁴².

Conclusions :

Using neutron reflection we have investigated the structure of a grafted PEG layer in the presence of water and in the presence of an aqueous solution of bovine serum albumin. The PEG surface was produced using a one-shot, base-promoted coupling reaction between the surface silanol groups and a trimethoxysilyl end-group of the PEG molecule with $M_w = 5000 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$. Characterisation of the PEG surface reveals that the grafting density is $\Gamma_{\text{PEG}} = 0.9 \pm 0.2 \text{ mg m}^{-2}$ and the thickness of the layer is $\sim 85 \text{ \AA}$ corresponding to $2\text{--}3 \times R_g$, placing the grafted layer in the weak brush regime. Despite the grafting solution being in a concentration regime where the PEG chains do not overlap, the grafting densities compare well with the densities obtained using a two-stage process whereby tressylated PEG is coupled on to an aminosilane coupled silica surface. No evidence was found for adsorption of BSA on to the PEG-treated silica surface, but in this respect neutron reflectometry is not overly sensitive to very low surface concentrations. However, the PEG layer was distinctly observed to change conformation and reduce its thickness when in the presence of the BSA solution. This resulting film compression is consistent with the conjectured mechanism for the

protein resistance of PEG as a steric-stabilization effect.

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